

Academic Buoyancy As A Predictor Of The Prince Sattam Bin Abdul-Aziz University Students' Attitudes Towards Using The Blackboard System In E-Learning

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Abstract

The current study aims at identifying the level of the Prince Sattam bin Abdul-Aziz University students' attitudes towards using the blackboard system, determining the extent to which academic buoyancy can predict the students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning, and the differences according to gender and academic disciplines both variables. The research sample consisted of (243) male and female students from the Prince Sattam bin Abdul-Aziz University. The researchers applied the academic buoyancy scale and the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system on the e-learning (prepared by the researchers). The researchers utilized the descriptive-analytic research approach. Results revealed that academic buoyancy contributed to predicting students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system and that there was a positive correlative relationship between academic buoyancy and students' attitudes towards using this system. Besides, students have a high level of attitudes towards using this system. Besides, there were no significant differences in both variables due to gender or academic discipline. Results of this research can be utilized in developing students' skills to face the academic pressures and challenges as well as enhancing their ability to solve problems they encounter through developing their academic buoyancy. It can be used also in developing the university students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning.

1. Introduction

The world is now experiencing a technological revolution and intelligence explosion, which left their mark upon the personal, professional, and educational areas of life. The most affected area is the education sector where e-learning has become a gate to develop the educational process and to transform it from the memorization phase to the creative, interactive, and skill development phase (Junior et al., 2019; Abdellatif, 2020; Croxton, 2014). In this context, University education is witnessing a huge demand for e-learning, especially after the emergence of the pandemic of Corona Virus (COVID-19). That e-learning becomes an urgent need because of imposing students' home lockdown during the learning process. Consequently, most Saudi universities, including Prince Sattam bin Abdul-Aziz University resorts to using e-learning via the Blackboard system.

The Blackboard System relies on designing courses, assignments, tasks, tests, and corrections electronically, as well as communicating with students through the virtual environments and applications downloaded via smartphones or computers (Melhem et al., 2018). Students tend to e-learning in general and learning through the Blackboard system in particular due to its advantages and comfort. It saves students time and effort as well as eliminating time and spatial barriers (Hew et al., 2018; Sivo et al., 2018). Besides, it provides the flexibility of participation and ease of access (Croxton, 2014).

Despite the above-mentioned advantages, e-learning is witnessing high student dropout rates, a waste of the educational institution resources, a significant cost for students as well as staff members, and the institution as a whole (Ali et al., 2018). It has become a concern for faculty members because of students' persistence in the learning process (Croxton, 2014). Moreover, the e-learning environment may not be suitable for all students; that for instance, the academically distinguished students prefer to study in traditional face-to-face classes (Sivo et al., 2018). E-learning increases the extraneous cognitive load and raises some learners' anxiety levels (Hong et al., 2017).

Hence, students may differ in their attitudes towards e-learning in general, and the use of the Blackboard system in e-learning in particular, because e-learning associates with some psychological factors that can affect the teaching process and the students' attitudes towards e-learning; that the student in e-learning needs a high degree of self-organization and self-motivation (de Barba, 2016; Almoeather, 2020). They also need perceived self-efficacy, learner autonomy, self-confidence (Gutiérrez-Santiuste & Gallego-Arrufat, 2016; Valencia-Arias et al., 2018), and perseverance (Sivo et al., 2018). Accordingly, the study of psychological factors that may

affect students' attitudes towards the use of the Blackboard system in e-learning must be taken into consideration to improve their attitudes, and invest the students' energies and capabilities in the e-learning process.

Academic Buoyancy is one of the psychological factors that help students deal with academic challenges positively. Recent research defines this term as the student's ability to negotiate successfully with daily academic stresses and swings up and down with it until he overcomes and goes up ([Martin & Marsh, 2008a](#); [Martin & Marsh, 2009](#); [Rodrigues & Magre, 2018](#)). Previous studies have agreed on the direct positive impact of academic buoyancy in academic attitudes (adherence to classroom rules, as well as the absence of subversive behaviors, participation in school assignments, exertion, focus, attention, perseverance, participation in school activities, and enjoyment of the task that yield positive student attitudes towards academic performance) as ([Martin et al., 2013](#); [Martin, 2013](#); [Martin, 2014](#)) studies. Academic buoyancy can contribute to emotions and attitudes through promoting positive feelings, such as enjoying learning ([Martin et al., 2017](#)). It also helps to control negative emotions such as anxiety ([Martin et al., 2010](#); [Collie et al., 2017](#)). In this context, the results of [Riikka et al. \(2019\)](#) indicated that academic buoyancy supports positive expectations and adaptive behaviors in learning situations by regulating academic emotions.

There is a logical relationship between academic buoyancy and attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning. Furthermore, these variables play a significant role in developing and improving different learning outcomes for learners in the e-learning setting. So that, investigating academic buoyancy reflects a recent trend in the field of developing students' skills to encounter challenges, setbacks, and academic pressures that must be taken into consideration to avoid its negative effects on the educational process, especially in the field of e-learning as a new experience at the Prince Sattam bin Abdul-Aziz University and within the limits of the researchers, there are no Arabic or foreign studies dealing with the academic buoyancy and the students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system. Therefore, the researchers seek to conduct this research to identify the Prince Sattam Bin Abdul-Aziz University students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning, the relationship between the academic buoyancy and attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning, the extent to which the academic buoyancy can predict attitudes towards the Blackboard system, and the differences in the academic buoyancy and attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning in the light of gender and academic discipline variable. Specifically, the results of the previous studies differ in the presence of the differences in academic buoyancy, and the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system according to gender and specialization contradict.

Literature review

Academic buoyancy refers to the students' ability to successfully deal with setbacks and challenges that serve as a model for the normal functioning of school life, for example, weak grades, exam stress, school assignments difficulty, and negative reactions ([Martin & Marsh, 2008a](#); [Martin et al., 2010](#); [Datu & Yuen, 2018](#); [Riikka et al., 2019](#)). The researchers defined the academic buoyancy procedurally as the ability of university students to effectively manage challenges and face the academic pressures they encounter through conscious planning. It is measured procedurally by the degree which the students obtain on the academic buoyancy scale prepared by the researchers. It included the following domains (self-efficacy, coping with stress, academic engagement, and planning). The researchers defined the dimensions of the academic buoyancy procedurally as follows:

- *Self-efficacy*: It is the set of judgments issued with a student that expresses his beliefs about his ability to learn and perform the tasks assigned to him with confidence and perseverance.
- *Resisting pressures*: The student's ability to encounter the pressures he faces flexibly and calmly, and to overcome the difficulties he faces positively.
- *Academic engagement*: It refers to perseverance, enjoyment of study, class participation, and good relations with teachers and colleagues.
- *Planning*: The student's ability to define his goals accurately and strive to achieve them in the light of thoughtful practical steps.

Academic buoyancy represents one of the successful mechanisms and psychological factors that contribute to expecting students' success and behavior directed to accomplishing tasks indirectly through creating a positive emotional atmosphere in learning situations. Several studies concerned with investigating the significance of academic buoyancy such as [Rikka's et al., \(2019\)](#) study which revealed that academic buoyancy supports positive expectations and adaptive behaviors in the learning situations through organizing emotions and is positively related to the enjoyment of mission and hope, while negatively related to the failure of expectations. [Rodrigues & Magre \(2018\)](#) indicated a positive correlation between buoyancy and students' participation in classes. Also, [Abdin's \(2018\)](#) study asserted that academic buoyancy affects indirectly academic accountability through test anxiety as a mediator variable.

The blackboard e-learning management system is an integrated system that manages the educational process synchronously and asynchronously. It provides a safe and easy way to use the learning environment. It helps the faculty members to present their courses and lectures through attaching multimedia (text, images, audio, video, and graphics). Through the Blackboard system learners group to browse the content, each according to their needs, and communicate with each other with multiple communication tools (e-mail, forums,) without the

limits of time and place, or through virtual classes from any type of smart device ([AlSadhan, 2015](#)). It refers to the materials that the instructor teaches on the websites which allow the learners to continue learning as it provides interaction and communication between teacher and learner to achieve joint learning in a fun way ([Belanger, 2004](#)). While [Ghazala and Elsaied \(2019\)](#) defined it as a system for managing e-learning via the internet and this is the system that is approved by Al Jouf University. It presents materials, courses, and tools for displaying the content and lectures through many multimedia and facilitates interaction between the student and the faculty members. The learning process happens simultaneously or asynchronously at any time and anywhere.

The positive attitude of students towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning reflects a good indicator for using it effectively in the future, and benefiting from it in developing their research and academic skills as well as developing their self-motivation. [Al-Shannaq and Doumi \(2010\)](#) defined the attitude towards the Blackboard in e-learning as the amount of emotional intensity shown by the members of the study sample towards e-learning by refusing, acceptance, or hesitation. [Ghazala and Elsaied \(2019\)](#) defined it as the degree of students' willingness to accept, reject, or hesitate to use the Blackboard system in e-learning. While as, the researchers defined it procedurally in the current research as the degree of students' willingness to accept, reject, or hesitate to the Blackboard system in e-learning in the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University. It is measured procedurally with the degree the student obtains on the scale of the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning prepared by the researchers. The researchers determined the dimensions of the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system as follows:

- *The attitude towards targeted learning outcomes through the Blackboard system in education:* The student's opinion on achieving the Blackboard system for the learning outcomes required in the educational process (knowledge, skills, and competencies).
- *The attitude towards the importance of the Blackboard system in education:* The student's opinion on the importance and feasibility of using the Blackboard system in education.
- *The attitude towards the quality of the performance of the faculty members in the educational process through the Blackboard system:* The student's opinion on the achievement of faculty members for their teaching tasks and interaction with their students efficiently through the Blackboard system.
- *The attitude towards effective use and ease of dealing with the Blackboard system in education:* The student's opinion on the possibility and ease of using the Blackboard system without obstacles in the educational process.\

Students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning directly affects their understanding and achievement ([Gazala and Al-Sayed, 2019](#)). Also, when applying and using new technology the attitudes significantly affect the efficiency of this system. It also may be the main reason for the success of applying this new technological system ([Al-Halfawi, 2009](#)). Regarding the importance of studying attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning and its relationship to psychological and demographic variables, several studies have been conducted to investigate such variables. In this context, [Al Balasy's study \(2016\)](#) observed high positive attitudes towards the use of the Blackboard system in e-learning and stated that there were no statistically significant differences in the students' attitudes according to gender or specialization. Furthermore, [Al-Husseini \(2015\)](#) confirmed that the students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning were positive and that the attitudes are higher in males than females in all the scale axes. [Uziak et al., \(2018\)](#) study results indicated that students were generally satisfied with the Blackboard system, that their performance improved as well as communication with the trainer was significantly enhanced. Besides, [Jabli \(2020\)](#) concluded that Saudi students with scholarships find difficulties in conforming to the educational system of the host country and that the most important difficulties in e-learning are that it is a new experience for them and they are not well prepared.

Moreover, [Alrefaai \(2019\)](#) showed that students' attitudes towards e-learning were positive and there was a significant difference in attitudes in favor of female students. While [Julian et al., \(2020\)](#) study results revealed positive attitudes of students towards the Blackboard system in e-learning as an attractive method that allows exchanging notes and sharing ideas through a virtual community. [Almoeather \(2020\)](#) also demonstrated that there were statistically significant differences between the means of the pre-post measurements of the self-organized learning in the Blackboard system scale in favor of the post-measurements, and there was a statistically significant difference between the means of the scores of the pre-post measurements of the educational satisfaction of the Blackboard system in favor of the post-measurement.

Most studies dealing with these variables in e-learning educational settings in general, and which indicated that it is a new idea, and that motivated the researchers to conduct this research. So that the current study hypothesizes the following:

- There is a statistically significant moderate level of attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning among students of the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University.

- There is no statistically significant correlative relationship between the degrees of the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students on the academic buoyancy scale with its dimensions, and the total degree of the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning and its dimensions.
- Attitudes towards using the Blackboard e-learning cannot be predicted statistically with the information of the participants' from the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students' degree on the academic buoyancy scale.
- There are no statistically significant differences between the means of those with high and low levels of academic buoyancy at the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system e-learning.
- There are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the academic buoyancy scale, its dimensions, and the total degree due to the gender variable (male-female).
- There are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system scale, its dimensions, and the total degree due to the gender variable (male-female).
- There are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the academic buoyancy scale, its dimensions, and the total degree due to the academic discipline variable (literal- scientific).
- There are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system scale, its dimensions, and the total degree due to the academic discipline variable (literal- scientific).

2. Materials and Methods

In light of the study objectives and hypotheses, the researchers utilized the descriptive-analytical research approach, specifically the predictive correlative method to shed light on the relationship between the study variables and to predict the relationships between them. To verify the study tools (87) (female= 41, male=46) (mean age=21.56, standard deviation=1.61±) university students from the Prince Sattam bin Abdul-Aziz University were selected to verify the validity and reliability of the study tools to be applied to the basic study. To apply the research tools the researchers selected (243) university students from the same university (female=132, male=111) (the literary disciplines= 137, the scientific disciplines= 106); (mean age=21.34, standard deviation= 1.83±).

The researchers utilized the academic buoyancy scale and the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning prepared by the researchers. This matter followed several procedures until it reached the final form. They will be summarized as follows:

The Academic Buoyancy Scale

After reviewing the literature and the psychological heritage related to academic buoyancy and reviewing many related measures as ([Victoriano, 2016](#); [Martin & Marsh 2008a](#); [Piosang, 2016](#); [Amer, 2018](#); [Abdin, 2018](#); [Halim 2019](#); [Yun et al., 2019](#)) the researchers constructed the academic buoyancy scale for university students as a tool to achieve the study objectives. The preparation process followed these steps:

- The researchers determined the scale objective which is measuring the academic buoyancy among male and female students at Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University which contains the following dimensions: self-efficacy, resisting pressures, academic engagement, and planning. These dimensions were chosen because they are the dimensions most used in previous studies and most suitable for university students.
- *Verifying the psychometric properties of the scale*

The scale was presented in its initial form to (5) jury members from psychology and curricula & teaching methodology professors to determine the suitability of these phrases to measure the academic buoyancy of university students. They recommended that the scale items were appropriate to the nature of the students and their characteristics with an approval percentage of (100%), they were directly related to the dimensions of the academic buoyancy with an approval percentage of (80%), and clarity of instructions with the percentage of (100%). Therefore, the scale possesses content validity.

The researchers verified the scale construct validity by calculating the correlation of the degree of each item to the dimension to which they belong to (87) female and male students. The correlation coefficients ranged (0.618: 0.884), which was statistically significant at the level of (0.01) and this indicated the internal consistency of the scale components.

The researchers verified the factorial validity using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin(KMO) to ensure the suitability of the sample to perform the factorial analysis by Bartlett's formulations to ensure the suitability of the scale to factorial analysis ([Glen, 2016](#)). All results were greater than (0.7) and significant at the (0.01) level. The factorial analysis for the academic buoyancy scale was conducted using the basic components of the Hotelling method. Furthermore, the researchers followed the "Gutman" criterion to determine the number of factors, where the factor is essential if its latent root equals 1 or more. Consequently, the scale consisted of (20) items distributed in the six domains of the scale. The scale overall degree ranged from (20-100) scores according to

the 5-point Likert scale (5 strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neutral, 2 disagree, and 1 strongly disagree). It is clear from the foregoing that the results of the factor analysis are closely harmonized with the theoretical perception upon which the scale of psychological barriers with its components is based.

To ensure the academic buoyancy scale reliability the researchers utilized the Cronbach's Alpha on the sample assigned to verify the research tools consisting of (87) students from Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University. The reliability coefficients ranged from (0.740: 0.908) with alpha Cronbach and (0.637-0.850) with a split-half reliability method, which was high coefficients and statistically significant at (0.01) level. Consequently, the scale and its dimensions achieve high validity and reliability that enables it to be applied in the basic study.

The Attitude towards using the Blackboard in e-learning scale

After reviewing the literature and the psychological heritage related to the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system and reviewing many related measures as ([Al-Shannaq and Domi 2010](#); [El Sadhan, 2015](#), [Melhem, et al., 2018](#); [Gazala and Elsaied 2019](#); [Uziak, et al 2018](#); [Julian et al 2020](#); [Almoether 2020](#)) the researchers constructed the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system scale for university students as a tool to achieve the study objectives. The preparation process followed these steps:

- The researchers determined the scale objectives which is measuring the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning among male and female students at the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University which contained the following dimensions: the attitude towards targeted learning outcomes through the Blackboard system in education, the attitude towards the importance of the Blackboard system in education, the attitude towards the quality of the performance of the faculty members in the educational process through the Blackboard system, and the attitude towards effective use and ease of dealing with the Blackboard system in education. These dimensions were chosen because they are the most used in previous studies and most suitable for university students.

- *Verifying the psychometric properties of the scale*

The scale was presented in its initial form to (5) jury members from psychology and curricula & teaching methodology professors to determine the suitability of these phrases to measure the students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system. They recommended that the scale items were appropriate to the nature of the students and their characteristics with an agreement percentage of (100%), they were directly related to the dimensions of attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning with an agreement percentage of (80%), and clarity of instructions with the percentage of (100%). Therefore, the scale enjoys content validity.

The researchers verified the scale construct validity by calculating the correlation of the degree of each item to the dimension to which they belong to (87) female and male students. The correlation coefficients ranged (0.718- 0.916), which was statistically significant at the level of (0.01) and this indicated the internal consistency of the scale components. The researchers also calculated the internal correlation coefficients for the sub-dimensions and the overall degree, that all values were positive and significant at the (0.01) level, which indicated the internal consistency of the scale components.

The researchers verified the factorial validity using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin(KMO) to ensure the suitability of the sample to perform the factorial analysis by Bartlett's formulations to ensure the suitability of the scale to factorial analysis ([Glen, 2016](#)). All results were greater than (0.7) and significant at the (0.01) level. The factorial analysis for the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system was conducted using the basic components of the Hotelling method. Furthermore, the researchers followed the "Gutman" criterion to determine the number of factors, where the factor is essential if its latent root equals 1 or more. Consequently, the scale consisted of (20) items distributed in the six domains of the scale. The scale overall degree ranged from (20-100) scores according to the 5-point Likert scale (5 strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neutral, 2 disagree, and 1 strongly disagree). It is clear from the foregoing that the results of the factor analysis are closely harmonized with the theoretical perception upon which the scale of the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system with its components is based.

To ensure the reliability of the attitude towards using the Blackboard system scale the researchers utilized the Cronbach's Alpha on the sample assigned to verify the research tools consisting of (87) students from Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University. The reliability coefficients ranged from (0.868: 0.965) with the Cronbach's Alpha and (0.820-0.932) with a split-half reliability method, which was high coefficients and statistically significant at (0.01) level. Consequently, the scale and its dimensions achieve high validity and reliability that enables it to be applied in the basic study.

3. Results and Discussion

The first hypothesis "There is a statistically significant moderate level of attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning among students of the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University "is tested. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers conducted statistical analyzes, where the arithmetic mean was calculated for the overall degree of the trend towards the use of blackboard in e-learning, and table 1 shows the results obtained:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Level of the Students' Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard system in e-learning n= (243)

Scale	Number of Items	Arithmetic Mean	Std.	The highest score	The lowest score	Relative Weight
Attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning.	20	73.31	19.79	100	20	73.31%

([Ibrahim & Abu Hashem, 2012](#))

Table 1 shows the following (n=243, mean=73.31, SD=19.79, the highest score=100, the lowest score=20) regarding the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning scale. Thus, the researchers concluded that the level of attitudes towards using the Blackboard system was high, where the relative weight reached(73.31%), which was a high percentage indicating that the students enjoy a high degree of attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in light of gender, literary and scientific disciplines and this is confirmed later in the subsequent hypotheses.

This result is consistent with the results of the following studies ([Uziak et al., 2018](#); [Alrefaai, 2019](#); [Gazala and Alsaied, 2019](#); [Julian et al., 2020](#)) which revealed that students' exhibit high positive level of attitudes towards the Blackboard system. While it differs from the [Jabli \(2020\)](#) study which concluded that, there is a low level of attitude towards using the Blackboard system. The researcher explained this high level of attitudes to the ease of use, students utilizing their technological accumulated experiences in learning through Blackboard, providing students with technical assistance on an ongoing basis, responding to their inquiries, and assisting them in solving their technical problems, the Deanship of IT providing training for students on using the Blackboard system, as well as providing continuous communication with the course professor. This is what confirmed by [Omar and Alnusabi \(2017\)](#) study that training on the Blackboard system in e-learning contributes to developing that attitudes towards using it and what [Ghazala and Elsaied \(2019\)](#) stated that the necessity and importance of this system contribute to developing positive attitudes towards using it. Researchers added also that this system becomes mandatory for Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students because of Coronaviruses to facilitate the educational process.

The second hypothesis" There is no statistically significant correlative relationship between the degrees of the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students on the academic buoyancy scale with its dimensions and the total degree of the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning and its dimensions" is tested. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers conducted the Pearson correlation coefficient. Table 2 shows the results obtained:

Table 2: Values of Correlation Coefficients between Academic Buoyancy and the Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard System in E-learning n= (243)

Academic Buoyancy	Self-efficacy	Resisting pressures	Academic engagement	Planning	The Total Degree
The Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard System					
The attitude towards targeted learning outcomes	**0.372	**0.312	**0.396	**0.363	**0.390
The attitude towards the importance of the Blackboard system	**0.431	**0.361	**0.413	**0.387	**0.431
The attitude towards the quality of the performance of the faculty members	**0.427	**0.367	**0.488	**0.369	**0.443
The attitude towards effective use	**0.376	**0.392	**0.371	**0.386	**0.411
The scale as a whole	**0.476	**0.423	**0.483	**0.453	**0.496

** Significant at 0.01 level ([Aldrich, 2018](#))

Table 2 clarified that there was a statistically significant correlative positive relationship at the (0.01) level between the academic buoyancy (dimensions and the total degree) and the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning (dimensions and the total degree) among the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students. This means rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis.

This finding is consistent with the studies of ([Martin et al., 2010](#); [Martin et al., 2017](#); [Collie et al., 2017](#); [Datu & Yuen, 2018](#); [Riikka et al., 2019](#)) which indicated that academic buoyancy contributes to emotions and attitudes by enhancing positive emotions such as enjoyment of learning, hope, positive expectations for success, and academic harmony. It also helps to control negative emotions such as anxiety, academic pressures, and negative reactions. The researchers attributed this result to the positive effects of the academic buoyancy and its dimensions that help students to create positive attitudes towards using the Blackboard system without fear or anxiety. Academic buoyancy contributes to achieving academic compatibility indirectly among students. While [Abdin \(2018\)](#) stated that academic buoyancy is reflected in the students' attitudes towards using the Blackboard system. Additionally, Academic buoyancy frees students from feelings of anxiety and makes them overcome the difficulties they face in the learning process as explained by ([Datu & Yuen, 2018](#)). Moreover, the attitude towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning depends on the psychological factor of the learner such as self-efficacy which influences students' satisfaction with their use of the Blackboard system.

The third hypothesis" Attitudes towards using the Blackboard e-learning cannot be predicted statistically with the information of the participants' from the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students' degree on the academic buoyancy scale "is tested. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers conducted simple regression analysis. Table (3) shows the results obtained:

Table.3: Simple Regression Analysis of Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard System in E-learning through Academic Buoyancy Degrees n= (243)

The Independent variable	The Dependent Variable	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	t value	Sig.	F value	Sig.	B Regression coefficient	Constant Variance	B value	Contribution degree
Academic Buoyancy	Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard System	**0.496	0.246	0.243	8.86	0.01	78.66	0.01	0.496	49.51	0.333	24.3%

** Significant at 0.01 level ([Ibrahim & Abu Hashem, 2012](#))

Table 3 presents the results of the regression analysis which revealed the rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis that attitudes towards using the Blackboard e-learning can be predicted statistically with the information of the participants' from the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students' degree on the academic buoyancy scale. The results demonstrated that the academic buoyancy scores (the independent variable) contribute to the dependent variable variance (the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system. That the correlation coefficient between the, reached (0.496), and that the academic buoyancy contributes to explaining the degree of variation in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system (24.3%) which means that (24.3%) of the variation in the degrees of the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning is due to the variation in the degree of the academic buoyancy. The F value percentage of this correlation was (78.66) which is significant at the 0.01 level and this indicates that the academic buoyancy degrees can predict students' degrees in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system, and the nature of the regression equation for predicting is as follows:

Dependent Variable= Constant value+ Regression coefficient * independent variable

Attitudes towards using the Blackboard system= 49.51+0.496* Academic buoyancy.

The previous result indicated that the increase in the academic buoyancy leads to an increase in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system and vice versa.

This finding is consistent with ([Martin et al., 2013](#); [Martin, 2013](#); [Martin, 2014](#)) studies which indicated the direct positive impact of academic buoyancy on academic achievement and educational orientations. The researchers attribute this result to the logical relationship between academic buoyancy and the attitude towards the use of the Blackboard system in e-learning. Furthermore, [Gomaa's \(2018\)](#) study indicated that academic motivation and high academic achievement can be predicted through academic buoyancy. While [Mahmoud's \(2018\)](#) study concluded that there is a relationship between adaptability and academic buoyancy. Besides, [Abdin's \(2018\)](#) study revealed that academic buoyancy affects academic compatibility indirectly through test anxiety. The researchers believe that academic buoyancy acts as a supportive force for the individual when facing situations that frustrate the completion of his academic career. Therefore it can be said that students who are characterized by high academic buoyancy can cope with academic challenges, which leads to a positive attitude towards learning in general and e-learning in particular.

The fourth hypothesis" There are no statistically significant differences between the means of those with high and low levels of academic buoyancy at the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system e-learning "is tested. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researchers conducted the following:

- Dividing the sample on the academic buoyancy scale into three levels based on the Cut of Points (low academic buoyancy from 20-68 degrees, average academic buoyancy 69-80 degrees, and high academic buoyancy 81-100 degrees).
- Using the t-test to verify the differences between the independent samples and the following table illustrates the results of this hypothesis:

Table.4: Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviations, the value of (t), and Its Significance for the Differences between High and Low Academic Buoyancy in the Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard in E-learning n=(243)

Dimensions	High/ low academic buoyancy students	n.	Mean	Std.	t-value	Sig.
The attitude towards targeted learning outcomes	Low academic buoyancy	78	14.38	5.82	6.85	0.01
	High academic buoyancy	75	20.44	5.08		
The attitude towards the importance of the Blackboard system	Low academic buoyancy	78	17.78	5.21	5.43	0.01
	High academic buoyancy	75	21.76	3.74		

The attitude towards the quality of the performance of the faculty members	Low academic buoyancy	78	15.69	5.47	6.02	0.01
	High academic buoyancy	75	20.72	4.83		
The attitude towards effective use	Low academic buoyancy	78	16.15	5.75	6.19	0.01
	High academic buoyancy	75	21.18	4.20		
The scale as a whole	Low academic buoyancy	78	46.01	20.21	6.67	0.01
	High academic buoyancy	75	84.10	16.93		

Tabulated $t=1.98$ at the level (0.05). ([Ibrahim & Abu Hashem, 2012](#))

Table 4 clarifies that this hypothesis has not been achieved and that there are statistically significant differences between the means of those with high and low levels of academic buoyancy at the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system e-learning.

This result can be explained through the fact that students with high academic buoyancy are characterized by optimism and ability to solve problems, social competence, and autonomy, and then they are characterized by a positive attitude towards the use of the Blackboard system in e-learning. This is what indicated by [Bilal\(2020\)](#) that those with academic buoyancy are characterized by positive expectations, the ability to adapt to academic situations, and academic engagement. This is also confirmed by ([Rodrigues & Magre, 2018](#); [Riikka et al., 2019](#)) studies. Moreover, individuals with high buoyancy have higher self-confidence, optimism, and adaptive ability which help them to deal with technology unlike those with low academic buoyancy who are anti-technology.

The fifth and sixth hypotheses" There are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the academic buoyancy scale, its dimensions and the total degree due to the gender variable (male-female) and there are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system scale, its dimensions and the total degree due to the gender variable (male-female)" are tested. To verify the validity of these hypotheses, the researchers utilized a t-test to verify the differences between the independent samples and the following table shows the results of these two hypotheses.

Table.5:: Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, (t) Value and Its Significance for the Differences between the Mean Scores of Males and Females in the Academic Buoyancy and the Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard System in E-learning

Dimension	Gender	n.	Mean	Std.	t-value	Sig.
Self-efficacy	male	111	18.64	4.22	0.89	not significant
	Female	132	19.11	3.74		
Resisting pressures	male	111	17.58	4.32	0.56	not significant
	Female	132	17.87	3.62		
Academic engagement	male	111	17.76	4.27	0.33	not significant
	Female	132	17.59	3.91		
Planning	male	111	19.42	3.98	0.002	not significant
	Female	132	19.42	3.23		
The total degree of the academic buoyancy scale	male	111	73.42	14.42	0.34	not significant
	Female	132	74.01	12.27		
The attitude towards targeted learning outcomes	male	111	17.00	6.37	0.29	not significant
	Female	132	17.23	5.62		
The attitude towards the importance of the Blackboard system	male	111	19.54	5.05	0.41	not significant
	Female	132	19.28	4.78		
The attitude towards the quality of the performance of the faculty members	male	111	17.63	5.73	1.54	not significant
	Female	132	18.68	4.56		
The attitude towards effective use	male	111	18.31	5.82	0.68	not significant
	Female	132	18.79	4.94		
The degree of the attitude scale	male	111	72.50	21.52	0.57	not significant
	Female	132	73.99	18.27		

Tabulated $t=1.98$ at the level of (0.05), tabulated $t=2.61$ at the level of (0.01) ([Aldrich, 2018](#))

Table 5 shows that these two hypotheses have been fully achieved and that there are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the academic buoyancy scale and the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system due to the gender variable (male-female).

The results of the fifth hypothesis are consistent with the studies of ([Selim, 2018](#); [Martin et al., 2010](#); [Jahedizadeh, et al., 2019](#); [Rezvani et al., 2019](#)) which revealed that there were no differences between males and

females in the academic buoyancy. In contrast, it differs from the results of (Halim, 2019; Martin & Martin 2008a; Datu & Yang, 2016; Collie et al., 2016) studies, which demonstrated that there were differences between males and females in the academic buoyancy in favor of males. Besides, it differs from the results of Martin & Marsh (2008b) study, which found that there were differences between males and females in academic buoyancy in favor of females. Results can be attributed to the nature of the circumstances and recent changes in education caused by the Corona pandemic which changes the educational system from relying on the traditional method to e-learning through the Blackboard system. This makes learners the core of the educational process, providing them with ways to learn and good training on using the Blackboard system without distinguishing between males and females.

Besides, results of the sixth hypothesis are consistent with Al-Balasy (2016) study whose results indicated that there are no fundamental differences between males and females in the attitudes towards the use of Blackboard in e-learning and inconsistent with the results of Ghazala and Elsieed (2019) and Alrefaie (2019) whose results indicated that there are significant differences between males and females in the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in favor of female students. It also differs from the study (Al-Hussein, 2015) whose results indicated that there are differences between males and females in the direction towards using blackboard in e-learning in favor of males. The researchers explain this result to the ease of dealing with the Blackboard system, and training students to the use the Blackboard without discrimination, and provide technical support to male and female students, in addition to providing facilities for male and female students to deal positively with the Blackboard system in light of the Corona pandemic through their presence in their homes.

The seventh and eighth hypotheses "there are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the academic buoyancy scale, its dimensions and the total degree due to the academic discipline variable (literal- scientific) and there are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system scale, its dimensions and the total degree due to the academic discipline variable (literal- scientific" are tested. To verify the validity of these hypotheses, the researchers utilized a t-test to verify the differences between the independent samples and the following table shows the results of these two hypotheses.

Table.5: Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, (t) Value and Its Significance for the Differences between the Mean Scores of students in the scientific and literary disciplines in the Academic Buoyancy and the Attitudes towards Using the Blackboard System in E-learning

Dimension	Discipline	n.	Mean	Std.	t-value	Sig.
Self-efficacy	literary	137	18.91	3.70	0.8	not significant
	scientific	106	18.87	4.31		
Resisting pressures	literary	137	17.78	3.65	0.15	not significant
	scientific	106	17.69	4.32		
Academic engagement	literary	137	17.78	3.95	0.47	not significant
	scientific	106	17.52	4.25		
Planning	literary	137	19.40	3.40	0.07	not significant
	scientific	106	19.44	3.82		
The total degree of the academic buoyancy scale	literary	137	73.89	12.46	0.19	not significant
	scientific	106	73.54	14.12		
The attitude towards targeted learning outcomes	literary	137	17.06	5.45	0.19	not significant
	scientific	106	17.21	6.60		
The attitude towards the importance of the Blackboard system	literary	137	19.24	4.60	0.53	not significant
	scientific	106	19.59	5.28		
The attitude towards the quality of the performance of the faculty members	literary	137	18.49	4.68	0.97	not significant
	scientific	106	17.83	5.68		
The attitude towards effective use	literary	137	18.61	4.90	0.12	not significant
	scientific	106	18.52	5.91		
The degree of the attitude scale	literary	137	73.42	17.75	0.9	not significant
	scientific	106	73.16	22.24		

Tabulated $t=1.98$ at the level of (0.05), tabulated $t=2.61$ at the level of (0.01) (Ibrahim & Abu Hashem, 2012) Table 5 shows that these two hypotheses have been fully achieved and that there are no statistically significant differences between the students' means of the scores on the academic buoyancy scale and the attitude scale towards using the Blackboard system due to the discipline variable (literary- scientific).

The result of the seventh hypothesis is consistent with Selim's (2018) study results which concluded that there are no differences in academic buoyancy due to the discipline (scientific - literary). The researchers attributed this result to the fact that the greater the level of the academic buoyancy among students, the more they have

skills to face school pressures and difficulties. Besides, students of the scientific and literary disciplines are similar in their endeavors to achieve themselves and their goals. Also, they have the same duties, pressures, and challenges.

This result is consistent with the study (Al-Balasy, 2016) whose results indicated that there are no fundamental differences between the scientific and literary disciplines in the direction towards the use of Blackboard in e-learning. This result can be explained by the fact that students of scientific and literary disciplines are similar in their educational conditions through the Blackboard system, so everyone receives technical support, and academic guidance alike without distinction, and due to the ease of use of the system and the training of all students on it contributed to the development of the trend towards using the Blackboard system for all Scientific and literary specialties. All of this coincided with the issuance of unified instructions from the university to all students of scientific and literary specializations in the way of learning, evaluation methods, and the system of questions. These instructions helped to form positive attitudes towards the Blackboard system among all students.

4. Conclusion

In the light of accepting or rejecting the above-mentioned study hypotheses, the researchers concluded that academic buoyancy of university students should be enhanced because it contributes to developing students' attitudes towards using the blackboard system in e-learning especially after proving the positive correlation between the two variables. Besides, the attitude towards the blackboard system use can be predicted with information about academic buoyancy. Hence, researchers suggested the necessity to develop students' skills to encounter the academic pressures and challenges through developing academic buoyancy. Moreover, the Prince Sattam bin Abdul Aziz University students enjoy a high level of attitudes towards using the blackboard e-learning due to the intensive training courses presented to them and that there were no differences in the level of academic buoyancy and attitudes towards using this system due to gender and the academic discipline as a result of the efforts devoted by the university for all students to develop their skills in e-learning. Undoubtedly, the success of e-learning depends on the psychological factors of the students, so planning and educational policies stakeholders in universities must be provided results related to the academic buoyancy to be developed through training programs, educational, and counseling strategies.

Limitations and study forward

Research tools were applied at the beginning of the summer semester of the academic year 2019/2020. The current study is a reflection of recent trends in the development of student skills to meet the challenges, setbacks, and academic pressures that must be taken into consideration to avoid its negative effects on the educational process, and therefore academic buoyancy can be used in the future research dealing with other variables to develop students' academic skills. Although there is a positive and statistically significant correlation between academic buoyancy and the attitudes towards using the Blackboard system in e-learning, this result requires confirmation through other studies of the same variables on other samples that use e-learning; as the case study, the community found facilities in learning through an assessment based on objective questions, taking tests without restrictions, and a small number of questions suitable to the test time. Therefore, researchers suggest conducting other research on the same variables with other samples that use e-learning and are interested in authentic assessment.

Authors' Contributions:

Abdellatif. M.S. formulated the main study problem and was responsible for data collection, reviewing the literature, designing study tools, and interpreting the study results. Alsharidah M.A. was responsible for reviewing the literature, conducting data statistical analysis, translating the article into English, and providing a conclusion.

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